

The Impact of Lending Interest Rate and Access to Credit on SME Growth: A Literature Review

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Abstract – An increase in lending interest rates means a rise in the price of borrowing money. It indicates a rise in the cost of running small and medium enterprises (SMEs) due to servicing of interest and eventually payment of the principal. This causes consumers to cut their expenditures leading to a fall in business sales. This is given that, high lending rates affect business through the influence on both their own direct costs and the ability of the SMEs to borrow and spend. The main objective of the study is to assess the access to credit by SMEs, as well as, how lending interest rate policy affects them. The results of this literature review indicate that the access to credit positively influences growth of SMEs. There is, as well, credit rationing as the lenders determine the amount of credit to allocate and interest to charge based on the probability of default. Finally low levels of credit demand by enterprise in are brought by lack of information about credit.

Keywords: Lending interest rate, Credit access, Literature review and SMEs.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship has been termed as an important tool towards economic development. Edmore (2011) argues that SME sector supported with conducive operational environment contributes prominently to economic growth through creation of employment opportunities, introducing innovation and entrepreneurship skills, generating higher production volumes and increasing exports. The dynamic role of SMEs in third world economies insures them as the main component through which the economic growth objectives of developing countries can be attained.

Otero and Rhyne, (1994) discuss that, in developed countries, for example, Germany's economy is characterized by well-developed SME sector, given that about two-thirds of the workers are employed by small and medium enterprises. In addition, in newly industrialized Asian countries, SMEs have become the main contributor towards their rapid economic growth. SMEs account for 99% of all enterprises and 88% of all employees in South Korea. Some of the world's leading large Korean companies such as Samsung and LG begun as small enterprises. From these examples, it is clear that SMEs are a driving force in the development process and that it would be rewarding for African countries to promote SMEs for further growth.

Celine (2005) argues that, Africa's SMEs have limited access to finance, which thus, hinders their emergence and eventual growth. The main sources of capital for African SMEs are retained earnings, informal savings and loan provisions, which are unpredictable. Wajohi (2009) and Kamau (2011) suggest that improving access to funding for small and medium-sized enterprises is important in encouraging entrepreneurship, competition, innovation and growth. Access to adequate capital to start, grow and further develop operational activities is a challenge faced by many SMEs in Kenya. This situation is compounded by the difficulties in accessing finance as SME financing is considered by many financial providers as a high risk activity that generates

high transaction costs and/or low returns on investment. Moreover, SMEs need to meet the challenge of adapting to the changing financial environment and the increasing complexity and extent of financial acquisition.

Lending Interest Rates and Accessibility of Funds

Ingram (2011) states that interest rates are important given that, they can be used to regulate the flow of money in the economy. High interest rates are useful in curbing inflation; however, tend to slow down the economic activities. Contrary to that, low interest rates stimulate the economy, but have a risk of triggering an inflation hike. When interest rates are high, people avoid loans from financial institutions because it is more draining to pay the loans back, and the number of purchase of real assets goes down. The opposite is also true. The effects of a lower interest rate on the economy are very beneficial for the consumer but not beneficial for lenders, who receive low returns on their loans than in times when interest rates are high. This means that banks may find themselves having to lower the interest rates accrued on money deposited in the bank in order to maintain a steady profit.

Atieno (2009) observes that access to finance from external sources is important for emerging SMEs to start and expand operations, develop new products, invest in new staff or production facilities. The availability of finance for investment is crucial to the sustainability and viability of new SMEs. Majority of upcoming SMEs depend on internal financing. Internal finance is often inadequate for new SMEs to survive and grow. It is increasingly difficult to keep the costs within the budget constraints of self-financing. Therefore new SMEs need capital from external sources. According to Demirguc-Kunt, Maksimovic, Beck and Laeven, (2006) the two primary sources of external finance for new SMEs are equity and debt. External equity in the form of venture capital or the stock exchange is usually not available for new SMEs. The lack of external equity makes many new SMEs dependent on bank loans and overdrafts and suppliers credit for early stage financing. Despite the dependence of SMEs on debt finance, paradoxically access to debt finance is very limited for new SMEs, especially in developing countries. Commercial banks and trade creditors hesitate to lend to new SMEs due to lack of collateral or trust.

Lending Interest Rate Policies and SME

Lending is one of the major activities from which commercial banks earn their profit by charging interest on amount lent (Asantey&Tengey, 2014). Commercial bank lending plays an important role in financing many businesses especially the SMEs, which are more dependent on traditional debt to fulfill their business financial needs (OECD, 2015). However, lending to SMEs by commercial banks poses the most serious credit risks. Credit risk constitutes the probability that loaned SME would default on interest and/or principal (Obamuyi, 2007). Credit risk is a major concern to all financial institutions that are involved in lending to SMEs because the risk of default by SME clients can sabotage the performance and survival of the lending institution (Ojiambo, 2012). It is, as well, believed that, small and medium enterprises as well as microfinance borrowers do not worry much about the level of lending interest rates charged on loans but, however, care mostly about the access of funding.

From the perspective of borrowers, lower lending rates have a high probability of increasing the potential demand for loans and financial inclusion, while high lending rates can push borrowers into over-indebtedness. From the perspective of microfinance institutions (MFIs), lower rates can make them more dependent on donors' money while high rates can lead to higher regulatory scrutiny and attract the worst borrowers adverse selection.

Literature Review

Marco et al (2021) investigates the importance of firm sector and country characteristics in credit access of SMEs in third world economies. The countries' characteristics related to the informational credit system and the financial institutions development is important in credit access. Informational characteristics of small and medium enterprises play an important role in determining the chances of accessing credit by SMEs. Similar to that, Magembe (2017) examines factors influencing access to credit by SMEs operators in Dar-es Salam. The study finds that the major challenges include high interest charged and collateral requirements. The study finds that, business information is as well a critical factor that largely influences credit access. Investigating the factors

that determine SME access to credit in Vietnam, Phuong (2012), uses the World Bank enterprise survey. Phuong finds that business depended on real estate and land as collateral to secure Credit. This was a problem to the small and medium enterprises in accessing credit from banks. Gladys (2012) study finds that not more than 20 percent of SMEs in Kenya have ever benefited from financial institutions through credit. Access is strictly regulated due to difficulties faced by the financial institutions in assessing SME risks in a cost effective manner. Financial institutions in Kenya address this risk-assessment challenge either by not giving credit to SMEs at all or by imposing collateral requirements and charging high rates of lending interest.

Bassey et al., (2014) examines the impact of bank lending and macroeconomic policy on the growth of Small Scale Enterprises in Nigeria. The findings revealed that bank lending and industrial capacity utilization brought a significant positive impact on the growth of Small Scale Enterprises. Similarly to that, Bello and Mohammed (2015) examined the impact of banking sector credit on the growth of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. The result reveals that banking sector credit has an important impact on the growth of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. Finally, Ibrahim and Ifeyinwa, (2020) examines the effects of bank lending on the growth of SME in Nigeria. The results indicate that lending to SME encourages self-employment, as well as, boosts industrialization leading to increase in economic activities and economic growth.

Kiring'a et al. (2021) investigates the effect of lending on access to financial services by SMEs in Kenya. The study finds that, lending plays a major role on the access to financial by SMEs. Ochanda (2014) sought to investigate the effects of financial sector regulation and financial innovation, inflation and general interest rates on growth of SMEs in Nairobi County. The study finds that access to credit was positively important in enhancing growth of 92% of SMEs. Most SMEs were found to face challenges in accessing credit due to high cost of finance and lack of collateral for the starters in entrepreneurship. Financial innovation was also positively important in influencing the progress of SMEs. Finally high financial sector regulation, inflation and interest rates were found to be a challenge on the growth of SMEs. As well, Muguchu (2013), sought to examine whether there exists a relationship between access to credit and financial performance of SMEs in Nairobi, Kenya. SMEs were sampled into clusters based on the streets where they are located. 40 SMEs sample within the central business district was selected for the survey. Analysis indicates that there was a positive relationship between access to credit and ROA. Kanyugi (2011) in assessing the impact of microfinance credit on the financial performance of SMEs in Kenya, finds that SMEs growth requires funds to finance growth in fixed assets and increase working capital. SMEs, therefore, are in need of longterm credit to enhance their capability to purchase raw materials, supplies and carry out activities necessary to facilitate production.

Credit rationing, as well, is found to influence credit demand to small-scale investors as reported by Okurut (2004). Okurut, focuses on determining factors that affect credit demand as well as those that result in the poor being rationed by financial institutions in Uganda. The findings indicate that it is possible most small and medium entrepreneurs, who seek credit would be able to obtain it, but the costs and conditions that come with loans, may be a hindrance for the high risk borrowers. Lenders tend to determine how much credit is allocated basing this on the probability of default, resulting in credit rationing. Adding to that, Swain (2002) discusses that, quantity rationing of loans arise when the potential borrower is denied credit while loan size rationing occurs when the loan amount received by the borrower is smaller than the one they demanded. Finally, Atieno (2001) pointed out that credit rationing behavior of lending institutions can be employed to explain the challenges of access to loans by SMEs. Atieno's study used mainly descriptive statistics to analyze the role of institutional lending policies of formal and informal credit institutions in determining access to and uses of credit facilities by small-scale entrepreneurs in rural Kenya. From the research findings, the major reasons for SMEs not to seek for credit from financial institutions were inadequate information about credit and lack of the required collateral. Only 49% of SMEs revealed their demand by applying for credit. Amongst this number, there were SMEs whose credit amount applied for was rationed and did not get the total amount applied for.

Kimuyu and Omiti (2000), in assessing institutional impediments to access to credit by micro and small scale enterprises in Kenya, finds that female-owned and informal entrepreneurs are more inclined to borrowing, however, they request for smaller amounts and enjoy lower success rates. While older and more educated entrepreneurs seek for and receive more credit than the younger and less educated. As well, Spatial and size differences abound in the inclination to seek out credit and in the success rates whereby urban-located and larger

enterprises have higher success rates and receive more credit than others. Therefore, choices of credit sources depend on formality status, gender, location, activity type and networking of SMEs.

Discussion

The literature reviewed indicates that there is agreement among policy makers and scholars that SMEs contribute largely towards economic development through creation of employment opportunities; generating higher levels of production hence increased income, increasing the amount of exports and promotion of innovation. From the literature reviewed, the paper finds that access to credit positively influences growth of SMEs. However, most of the SMEs faced challenges of high cost of finance and lack of collateral. This is given that, access to credit is regulated due to challenges in assessing SME risk in a cost effective manner. Lenders, therefore, tend to address this by either not lending to SME or requiring collateral and charging high interest rates. There is, as well, credit rationing as the lenders determine the amount of credit to allocate and interest to charge based on the probability of default. Finally low levels of credit demand by enterprise in are brought by lack of information about credit.

Conclusion

With the ever increasing need for SMEs to have credit empowerment, there is an importance to invest in proper credit access strategies so as to meet these expectations. This should be done in a direction that favors all the stakeholders. This, therefore, calls for adopting well drafted credit access strategies which are acceptable, accessible, and ethically sound and have a positive perceived impact on the growth of SMEs. The management of lending institutions should ensure that they carry out a research on businesses information to establish ideal interest rates to be charged without compensating for probability of default. This will improve the competitiveness of financial institutions and as well enhance the customer- financial institution relationship.. Lending institutions should also invest on the advisory programs to borrowers on how to appraise their projects for viability so that they can perform well and avoid loan defaulting. This will go a long way in helping and training the business owners to realize the objectives of the business and the credit to yield high returns. Banks and government funding agencies should engage professional marketers of credit facilities to help SMEs understand the criteria and requirements to access funds. This will create awareness among SMEs about credit facilities as the institutions get informed as well on consumers preferences.

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